

THE ROLE OF ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS IN THE MEDIA

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Abstract: Today, environmental problems are one of the issues that concern all of us. It is important for us to get information about them. This article talks about the role and importance of the media in obtaining information about environmental problems.

Key words: Environment, media, news, awareness, education

Introduction: No matter what field it is, it is important to quickly convey information about it to the society. In particular, the role of the media in disseminating information about the environment is significant. The media plays a crucial role in raising environmental awareness and promoting sustainability. Through various channels such as television, radio, newspapers, magazines, and online platforms, the media has the power to inform and educate the public about environmental issues.

In the past decades, sustainability and environmental awareness have gained media attention. Due to increasing media coverage, our society is becoming more aware of the effects that our activities put on the health of the environment. In this regard the media has a big role to play in making people aware of environment issues and taking actions to protect the environment. Mass Media plays an important role for creating environment awareness among people. Environment is the basic need of life like food and water. But our actions have aggravated it severely. Realizing our mistake we have taken commendable steps to reform it and a proper media attention might give a higher success rate to any mission related to environment. [1]

In today's era of globalization, as the types of media are increasing, the speed of information delivery is also increasing. People find it more convenient to get information from social networks than newspapers or television.

Environmental awareness through social media is a easier and faster way to communicate people and groups about the environmental issues. It is the group of internet-based platform which build on technological foundation of web 2.0 and which allow exchange and sharing of user generated content.[2] Social media platforms are also utilized by industry and government agencies as a preferred tool of communication with the general public. The print, broadcast, and Internet media can be a powerful ally in educating the public on environmental matters. In order to perform this role effectively, it is often necessary for the Government to work with the media (and sometimes educate the media). This is often done informally, through regular briefings and information centres. Media has a big role to play in making people aware of environment issues and taking actions to protect the environment.[3]

In fact, Social media platforms also play a significant role in spreading awareness about environmental issues. People can share information about environmental challenges and solutions with a wide audience through social media networks.

But, Both media can be very effective environmental communication tools, but until now they have not been used enough. Most environmental documentaries on television today attract few viewers because of their academic or pedantic presentation. Environmental reporting can do a lot to raise awareness. The concept of environmental protection is a reality related to coping and subsistence. A number of print and broadcast magazines offered environmental columns and programs. However, the overall coverage is quite rudimentary and limited. Now the focus is on environmental reporting. Mass media can provide general information about waste related to the environment. The media can be a tool to break the silence around environmental issues and create an environment that encourages discussion about how the community can participate and change their behavior. It is very important to raise public awareness of environmental issues. The efforts of the press to raise public awareness of environmental problems and its continuing central role in combating the causes of environmental problems are important. [4]

The majority claim to pay proper media attention and declare they are aware of environmental education through media sources, yet it's very hard for people to take responsibilities in taking major actions to conserve the environment. Media has attempted to provide information that has impact on how we should save the environment from the hands of unethical people. [5] For the saving of our nature, environmental awareness performs

critical role among environmentalist, regulatory authorities, government and non-government organization, academicians, researchers, students for creating interest in environment. The environmental awareness leads to environmental protection. Offline Media Communication and Environmental Awareness In the case of offline media, different newspapers communicate as the predominant media which influence the people for various ages and can play a greater role in the environmental awareness and protection of the environment. [6]

From the above points, we realized how important the role of the media is in raising awareness about the environment today. To what extent has this issue been resolved in Uzbekistan? The question arises as to how quickly and transparently environmental issues are covered in the Uzbek media. As an answer to this question, we can quote this sentence from Article 49 of the newly revised Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. "Everyone has the right to a comfortable environment, reliable information about his condition".

In conclusion, the media has a powerful influence in shaping public opinion and behavior towards environmental issues. By raising awareness and promoting sustainable practices, the media can contribute to fostering a culture of environmental responsibility.

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